

A Prospective and Observational Study of Induction of Labour Versus Expectant Management in Over date Pregnancies amongst Indian Women

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Abstract:**Background:** This study compared expectant management (EM) up to 41 weeks to elective induction of labor (e-IOL) in overdate pregnancies (40 1/7 to 40 6/7 weeks). It was a prospective observational study. The primary objective was to compare the rate of Caesarean section in the two groups.**Methods:** In this study women who met the inclusion and exclusion criteria at 40 weeks of pregnancy were enrolled in the study. There were 112 women in total in the sample. 56 participants in the e-IOL group 1 were induced between 40 1/7 and 40 6/7 weeks of gestation, while 56 participants in the EM group 2 received expectant care until 41 weeks of gestation. Group 2 was further subdivided as follows: Group 2a consisted of women who spontaneously went into labor while under expectant care, and Group 2b consisted of women who were induced for maternal or fetal reasons or at least 41 0/7 weeks gestation while under expectant management.**Result:** The chance of spontaneous labor increased when expectant care was continued to 41 weeks of gestation past the due date, without negatively impacting the perinatal outcome. In the EM group, 73.2% of participants experienced spontaneous labor, and 78% of them gave birth vaginally. In our study, the rates of cesarean sections using EM (37.5%) were lower than those using e-IOL (58.9%) (p=0.002).**Conclusion:** Comparing elective induction of labor to expectant management, women with post-date pregnancies undergoing expectant management had lower rates of Caesarean section. There was no discernible difference in the perinatal outcomes of the two groups. Those on expectant management who experienced spontaneous labor had a higher chance of vaginal delivery.**Keywords:** Induction of labour, Overdate pregnancy, EM, e-IOL.

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Introduction

A pregnancy is considered post-term if it has progressed or reached 42 weeks of gestation after the last menstrual period (LMP). Following 41 weeks of pregnancy, there is a progressive increase in perinatal mortality and neonatal morbidity, with a more pronounced increase occurring around 42 weeks. [2] It is controversial to treat pregnant women who continue to carry their pregnancy after the estimated date of delivery (EDD). Such a pregnancy carries a slight but serious risk to the fetus. While postponing it raises the risk of stillbirth, fetal distress, and neonatal morbidity, an earlier induction of labor (IOL) may expose the mother to a risk intrinsic to induction of labor, including a possible more operative intervention and its accompanying morbidity. [3,4] The majority of guidelines suggest 42 weeks gestation for birth and offer prenatal surveillance along with labor

induction between 41 0/7 and 41 6/7 weeks. [1] There is diversity in the length of pregnancy depending on the mother's ethnicity. For Black and Asian women, the median gestational age at delivery is approximately 39 weeks. [5]. As a result, a lot of obstetricians in our nation favor inducing pregnancy in women as soon as 40 1/7–40 6/7 weeks together with the woman. Most of studies comparing induction of labor with expectant management has been done at 41 weeks of gestation, however the evidence that is now available shows that induction of labor does, in fact, lower the rate of Caesarean section. [6,7]

Materials and Methods

This prospective observational study was done at Department of Obstetrics Gynaecology, ESIC Medical College and Hospital, Bihta, Patna, Bihar from June 2022 to December 2023. Pregnant women who were admitted to our hospital at 40 weeks of gestation satisfying the inclusion and exclusion criteria were recruited for the study after taking an informed consent. The study being an observational study, no intervention was done for the purpose of study and clinical management was done as per different unit protocol. The sample size of 112 was based on the statistical calculation of the data from the past records of the hospital over 2 months, keeping primary objective in view (Caesarean section rates) {Two sided confidence level(1-alpha) – 95; Power (% chance of detecting) - 80}. All pregnant women at or beyond 40 0/7 weeks (overdate) admitted in the hospital were included in this study.

Overdate pregnancies with diabetes, hypertensive disorders of pregnancy, cardiac or renal disease, congenital anomalies, fetal growth restriction, obesity, oligohydramnios, women with suboptimal dating of pregnancy (Unsure LMP and nonavailability of early sonography) and who refuse to give consent for the study were excluded in this study.

The two groups to be compared were labelled as:

1. Group 1: Elective Induction of labour between 40 1/7 to 40 6/7 weeks of gestation (e-IOL).
2. Group 2: Expectant management till 41 weeks of gestation (EM). Group 2 was further subdivided to assess the outcome of different lines of management in the expectant group.
 - i) Group 2a: Who went into spontaneous labour while on expectant management.
 - ii) Group 2b: Who were induced while on expectant management for maternal/ fetal reasons or ≥ 41 0/7 weeks of gestation.

The Elective induction Group 1 was observed for the method of induction used, mode of delivery and neonatal outcomes. All the participants in the elective induction group were offered IOL at 40 1/7

to 40 6/7 weeks. The Expectant Management Group 2 was monitored with the antenatal fetal surveillance in the form of twice weekly Non-stress test (NST) and Amniotic fluid index (AFI). Expectant management Group was further observed for spontaneous onset and progress of labour, need for IOL for maternal or fetal reasons, the mode of delivery and the neonatal outcome. All participants in the expectant management group were offered induction at or immediately after 41 0/7 weeks of gestation.

Other intrapartum events such as abnormal cardiotocography (CTG), meconium passage and labour progress disorders were noted. Fetal outcome evaluated were Apgar score at 1 and 5 minutes, baby weight, need for NICU admission and neonatal problems.

Data entry was done in MS Excel 2020 and was analyzed using professional statistics package EPI Info 17.0 version for Windows. Descriptive data was represented as mean \pm SD for numeric variables, percentages and proportions for categorical variables. Appropriate tests of significance was used depending on nature & distribution of variables like Chi square test, Fisher exact test for categorical variables, independent t test for numerical variables. Values of $p < 0.05$ was considered statistically significant.

Results

A total of 112 participants were recruited in the study in accordance to sample size calculation. Group 1 had 56 patients who underwent elective induction of labour at 40 1/7 to 40 6/7 weeks (e-IOL).

Group 2 also had 56 participants who were given expectant management till 41 weeks of gestation (EM). The mean age of participants in e-IOL group 1 was 26.6 \pm 3.34 years and EM Group 2 was 25.55 \pm 2.75 years respectively. Both the groups were comparable ($p=0.067$). Primigravida and multigravida were comparable in both groups (Table 1).

Table 1: Distribution of participants according to gravidity in elective induction Group 1 and expectant management Group 2

Gravida	Group 1	Group 2
Primigravida	62.5%	71.4%
Multigravida	37.5%	28.6%

In the e-IOL Group 1, all the 56 participants were induced, whereas in EM Group 2, 41 (73.2%) went into spontaneous labour and 15 (26.8%) were induced. (Table 2)

Table 2: Distribution of participants according to the type of labour in expectant management EM Group 2

Type of Labour	No. of cases (n=56)	Percentage
Spontaneous	41	73.2%
Induced	15	26.8%

In the e-IOL group 1, maximum were induced at 40 2/7 weeks of gestation (16 participants, 28.5%) and 40 3/7 weeks of gestation (16 participants, 28.5%).

Among the 41 participants in the EM group who went into spontaneous labour (Group 2a), 24.4% went into spontaneous labour at 40 2/7 weeks (10 participants) followed by 21.9% (9 participants) at 40 1/7 weeks of gestation. Amongst EM (15 participants, 26.8%) Group 2b, 3 participants were induced in view of maternal/fetal reasons and 12

(80%) were induced at 41 weeks of gestation as they did not go into spontaneous labour. In the e-IOL Group 1, 23 participants (41.07%) delivered vaginally and 33 underwent caesarean section (58.93%).

Whereas in EM (Group 2), 35 participants delivered vaginally (62.5%) and 21 participants underwent caesarean section (37.5%). There is statistical difference in the mode of delivery ($p=0.002$) (Table 3).

Table 3: Distribution of mode of delivery in elective IOL (Group 1) and expectant management (Group 2)

Mode of delivery	Group 1 e-IOL (No., %)	Group 2 EM (No., %)
Vaginally	23 (41.07%)	35 (62.5%)
Caesarean	33 (58.93%)	21 (37.5%)

In the EM (Group 2a), 32 participants (78%) delivered vaginally and 9 participants (22%) underwent Caesarean section. Among the 15 participants in the EM (Group 2b) who underwent IOL, 8 of 12 (66.6%) who underwent induction at 41 weeks of gestation ended in Caesarean delivery while one amongst the 3 (33.3%) participants induced due to oligohydramnios on fetal surveillance, underwent Caesarean section.

Most participants in the e-IOL (Group 1) were induced with foley catheter (n 35, 62.5%), and followed by 0.5 mg of endocervical dinoprostrone gel (n 21, 37.5%). Amongst 31 participants induced at 40 weeks of gestation with foley catheter, 15 (48.3%) delivered vaginally while only 3 (17.6%) delivered vaginally after dinoprostrone gel induction. In the EM (Group 2b), 8 participants who were induced at 41 weeks of gestation with

foley catheter, 50% delivered vaginally. 3 participants were induced with dinoprostrone vaginal pessary, all of them underwent Caesarean section for delivery.

In e-IOL group 1 most common indication of Caesarean section was non-progress of labour followed by failure of induction and meconium-stained amniotic fluid (MSF) and in EM (Group 2), refusal for further continuation of IOL was the most common indication for Caesarean section. 12 of 56 participants in the e-IOL (Group 1) had meconium stained liquor. 2 delivered vaginally and 10 underwent Caesarean section. In EM (Group 2a), 8 participants had meconium stained liquor, out of which 2 delivered vaginally and 6 underwent Caesarean section. And in EM (Group 2b), 3 patients had meconium stained liquor, and all 3 underwent Caesarean section (Table 4).

Table 4: Analysis of meconium stained amniotic fluid in elective induction of labour (Group 1) and expectant management (Group 2) with the mode of delivery

MSF	Elective induction of labour (Group 1)		Expectant management spontaneous (Group 2a)		Expectant management induced (Group 2b)	
Vaginal	2	16.67%	2	25.0%	0	0
LSCS	10	83.33%	6	75.0%	3	100.0%
Total	12	100.0%	8	100.0%	3	100.0%

Most women had babies weighing between 2.5 and 3.5 kg in e-IOL (Group 1) (85.7%) and similarly in EM (Group 2) 87.5%. Only one baby in the EM (Group 2) had birth weight more than 4 kg ($p=0.9$) and was delivered vaginally after foleys induction at 41 weeks of gestation. In the e-IOL (Group 1), 4 neonates were admitted to NICU for tachypnoea; out of which 3 had intrapartum MSF. In the EM (Group 2), 4 neonates were admitted to NICU, of whom 2 had neonatal tachypnoea, however they did not have intrapartum MSF. No other neonatal problems and neonatal deaths were noted ($p=1$).

Discussion

The timing of delivery is an important determinant of perinatal outcome. Early induction of labour is thought to expose the mother to a higher risk of

operative intervention (Caesarean section) especially in an environment where patience in labor is not the common approach. [8] On the other hand delaying induction in postdate pregnancy increases the incidence of stillbirth, perinatal morbidity and mortality. There is uncertainty on the timing of induction for pregnancies past their due date, leading to practice variation between obstetricians. [9] Formulating the best possible time to deliver a pregnancy necessarily involves balancing risks and benefits. The present study aimed to answer the research question whether induction of labour as compared to expectant management increases Caesarean section rates in pregnancies past their due date in a real-life situation. This observational study was done on 116 participants satisfying inclusion and exclusion

criteria. They were recruited at 40 weeks of gestation, 56 participants were recruited in e-IOL (Group 1) and the other 56 in EM (Group 2).

The mean age of participants amongst the two groups in the study was comparable. Maximum participants in both the groups were primigravida with no statistical difference amongst the two groups. Nulliparity is a known risk factor for post term pregnancies. [10] Most participants were induced in the first few days of being overdue in the e-IOL (Group 1) and also in the EM (Group 2) most went into spontaneous labour in the first few days of being overdue.

Although many past observational studies (Vrouenraets et al) [11] have found a higher risk for adverse outcomes with elective induction, these studies are suggested to have a methodological flaw. Such studies have been designed to compare IOL with spontaneous labor at the same gestational age, a comparison that is not clinically relevant and is potentially misleading. The actual clinical alternative comparator to IOL is not spontaneous labor but rather allowing the pregnancy to progress to a greater gestational age with expectant management. [12] Today, there are many randomized controlled trials (RCTs) which have compared routine IOL at 41 weeks and expectant management. They have found no differences in Caesarean section rates. [13,14]

In the present study which compared elective induction of labour at 40 weeks versus expectant management, expectant management till 41 weeks and then inducing labour at 41 weeks of gestation resulted in a significantly higher number of patients having vaginal delivery (62.5%) when compared with patients who were induced at 40 weeks (41.07%). In the present study foley catheter and dinoprostone gel, were the different methods of induction in the e-IOL (Group 1) whereas only foley catheter or dinoprostone vaginal pessary in EM (Group 2). Foley catheter was used for maximum patients in both the groups. Participants who underwent IOL by foley catheter both in the e-IOL and in the EM group were more likely to deliver vaginally compared to prostaglandins. Waiting till 41 weeks and then inducing labour did not have an effect on meconium staining of liquor in our study.

No significant difference in perinatal outcome was noted amongst those whose labour was induced as compared to those who were expectantly managed.

Conclusion

According to the present study, managing expecting mothers until 41 weeks of gestation raises the chance of spontaneous labor without having a negative impact on the perinatal outcome and reduces the risk of a Caesarean section.

References

1. Practice bulletin no. 146: Management of late-term and postterm pregnancies. *Obstet Gynecol.* 2014; 124(2):390–6.
2. Muglu J, Rather H, Arroyo-Manzano D, Bhattacharya S, Balchin I, Khalil A, et al. Risks of stillbirth and neonatal death with advancing gestation at term: A systematic review and meta-analysis of cohort studies of 15 million pregnancies. *PLoS Med.* 2019; 16(7):e1002838.
3. Gommers JSM, Diederer M, Wilkinson C, Turnbull D, Mol BWJ. Risk of maternal, fetal and neonatal complications associated with the use of the transcervical balloon catheter in induction of labour: A systematic review. *Eur J Obstet Gynecol Reprod Biol.* 2017; 218:73–84.
4. Chen W, Xue J, Peprah MK, Wen SW, Walker M, Gao Y, et al. A systematic review and network meta-analysis comparing the use of Foley catheters, misoprostol, and dinoprostone for cervical ripening in the induction of labour. *BJOG.* 2016; 123(3):346–54.
5. Papoutsis D, Antonakou, Angeliki, Tzavara C. The Effect of Ethnic Variation on the Success of Induced Labour in Nulliparous Women with Postdates Pregnancies. *Scientifica (Cairo).* 2016; 2016:9569725.
6. Hutcheon JA, Harper S, Strumpp EC, Lee L, Marquette G. Increasing rate of induction do not increase Caesareans: Using inter-institutional practice variation to understand the risks and benefits of routine labour induction at 41 weeks. *BJOG.* 2015; 122(7):973–81.
7. Mishanina E, Rogozinska E, Thatthi T, Uddin-Khan R, Khan KS, Meads C. Use of labour induction and risk of cesarean delivery: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *CMAJ.* 2014; 186(9):665–73.
8. Rydahl E, Eriksen L, Juhl M. Effects of induction of labor prior to post-term in low-risk pregnancies: a systematic review. *JBIC Database System Rev Implement Rep.* 2019; 17(2):170–208.
9. Nippita TA, Porter M, Seeho SK, Morris JM, Roberts CL. Variation in clinical decision-making for induction of labour: a qualitative study. *BMC Pregnancy Childbirth.* 2017; 17(1):317.
10. Deng K, Huang Y, Wang Y, Zhu J, Mu Y, Li X, et al. Prevalence of postterm births and associated maternal risk factors in China: data from over 6 million births at health facilities between 2012 and 2016. *Sci Rep.* 2019; 9(1):273.
11. Vrouenraets F, Roumen F, Dehing CJG, Akker E, Aarts MJB, Scheve EJT. Bishop score and risk of cesarean delivery after induction of labor in nulliparous women. *Obstet Gynecol.* 2005; 105(4):690–7.

12. Wood S, Cooper S, Ross S. Does induction of labour increase the risk of caesarean section? A systematic review and meta-analysis of trials in women with intact membranes. *Obstet Gynecol Surv.* 2014; 69(9):519–21.
13. Middleton P, Shepherd E, Crowther CA. Induction of labour for improving birth outcomes for women at or beyond term. *Cochrane Database Syst Rev.* 2018; 5(5):CD004945.
14. Wennerholm U, Saltvedt S, Wessberg A, Alkmark M, Bergh C, Wendel S, et al. Induction of labour at 41 weeks versus expectant management and induction of labour at 42 weeks (SWEdish Postterm Induction Study, SWEPIS): multicentre, open label, randomised, superiority trial. *BMJ.* 2019; 367:l6131.